

Iso-Surface Geometry from Tangent-Based Scalar Fields for Generative Design and

Fabrication

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Abstract

We explore the generation of organic-like sculptural forms from mathematical scalar fields, investigating iso-surfaces defined by $u = \tan(g)$ and $u = \frac{1}{\tan(g)}$, where the inner function $g(x, y, z) = z \tan(y) + x \tan(z) + y \tan(x)$ is designed to produce rotationally symmetric structures with distributed singular amplification. This cyclic cross-coupled structure was chosen to promote the emergence of interconnected branching geometries reminiscent of natural forms such as coral and fungal mycelium. Unlike conventional sine-cosine constructions, the tangent function introduces periodic singular behavior, enabling iso-surface geometries with localized sharp features that arise intrinsically from the scalar field structure rather than through explicit feature injection. The gradient decomposes into a geometric variation term from g and an amplification term from the outer trigonometric function; visualization confirms that both contribute throughout the surface with distinct spatial roles. Analysis of gradient magnitude versus distance to the singular set reveals large gradients near singular regions due to amplification, while substantial gradients at larger distances indicate that g independently generates strongly curved structures. Six models fabricated by 3D printing were selected to explore visually distinct sculptural qualities, including enclosure, branching, and flow; selected models were additionally produced in full-color and metal. These

results demonstrate that tangent-based scalar fields extend the design space of implicit surface modeling beyond conventional smooth and periodic constructions.

Keywords: implicit surfaces, iso-surfaces, generative art, mathematical sculpture, tangent-based scalar fields, singular amplification

Subject classification codes: Primary 00A66; Secondary 51N20, 68U05.

1. Introduction

Iso-surfaces derived from scalar fields have been widely used as a framework for generating three-dimensional forms in both scientific visualization and mathematical art.

Such surfaces are typically defined as level sets of scalar fields, where a surface corresponds to a set of points satisfying $u(x, y, z) = c$ for a scalar field u , separating the domain into interior and exterior regions [5].

Implicit surfaces have been extensively investigated in computer graphics and geometric modeling as flexible representations of complex three-dimensional geometry. The functional representation of geometric objects, in which shapes are defined as zero sets of continuous real-valued functions, provides a unified framework for set-theoretic operations, blending, and field-based modeling [6]. Building on this foundation, subsequent research established polygonization methods, blending operations, and hierarchical construction techniques — including the *BlobTree* — for constructing

smooth and controllable implicit forms [2,9]. These approaches established scalar-field modeling as a versatile framework for both scientific visualization and computational design.

Within this tradition, trigonometric functions have played an important role in defining periodic implicit surfaces. In particular, triply periodic minimal surfaces (TPMS) such as the gyroid, Schwarz P, and Schwarz D surfaces are commonly approximated using sine and cosine level set equations [1]. Research on implicit modeling has additionally examined methods for controlling localized geometric transitions and sharp features within scalar-field representations; prior work has shown that sharp edges and vertices can be introduced into otherwise smooth implicit surfaces through explicit augmentation of the underlying scalar field with edge and vertex descriptors [8]. In contrast to such externally imposed feature injection, the present study demonstrates that sharp features arise intrinsically from the mathematical structure of the scalar field itself.

Representative examples of smooth periodic implicit surfaces include the Schwarz P and D surfaces and the gyroid, which exhibit smooth periodic structures with well-controlled curvature. H.A. Schwarz established a foundational class of periodic minimal geometries. Later investigations by Alan Schoen expanded the known repertoire of such surfaces, identifying new families with intricate connectivity and spatial organization, among

which the gyroid has become particularly well known (Fig. 1a) [7].

The intersection of mathematical structure and sculptural form has been explored by a number of practitioners. Bathsheba Grossman has explored mathematically generated sculptural forms through 3D printing technologies, demonstrating how implicitly defined geometries can be realized as physical objects [3]. Representative examples are shown in Fig. 1b, c.

In contrast to these smooth formulations, the present study investigates scalar fields composed with tangent-based functions and their reciprocal counterparts. Unlike sine and cosine, the tangent function introduces singular behavior, leading to strong local amplification in the scalar field. This property enables the generation of geometric features that are sharper and more localized than those observed in conventional implicit surfaces. The inner function $g(x, y, z)$ was designed to introduce cyclic coupling among the three spatial coordinates while preserving rotational symmetry under cyclic permutation of the axes. Unlike separable formulations based on sums of independent trigonometric terms, each component of g couples a tangent singularity in one coordinate with linear variation in another. This cross-coupled structure produces spatially distributed amplification effects rather than isolated directional singularities. Because the tangent function diverges periodically at $x = \frac{\pi}{2} + k\pi$, $y = \frac{\pi}{2} + k\pi$,

and $z = \frac{\pi}{2} + k\pi$, the resulting scalar field contains a periodic lattice of singular regions.

The cyclic arrangement of these regions contributes to the emergence of interconnected sharp features and sculptural branching structures observed in the generated iso-surfaces.

The scalar field considered in this study is constructed as follows:

$$u(x, y, z) = \tan(g(x, y, z))$$

and its reciprocal form

$$u(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{\tan(g(x, y, z))}$$

where $g(x, y, z)$ is a trigonometric combination of spatial coordinates. The gradient of this field can be expressed as

$$\nabla u = A(g) \nabla g$$

where $A(g)$ denotes an amplification term arising from the outer trigonometric function.

Following the level set framework [5], we interpret this decomposition in terms of two geometric contributions — the intrinsic variation of g and the nonlinear amplification induced by the outer function — which jointly govern the resulting geometry. The gradient structure is analyzed both visually and quantitatively in subsequent sections to characterize these two mechanisms.

Figure 1. (a) Gyroid minimal surface discovered by Alan Schoen [7]. (b), (c) Gyroid sculpture by Bathsheba Grossman. Image courtesy of the artist [3].

2. Mathematical Formulation

We define the inner function g through a cyclic cross-coupling of the spatial coordinates:

$$g(x, y, z) = z \tan(y) + x \tan(z) + y \tan(x).$$

As noted in the Introduction, this specific construction is chosen for its cyclic symmetry under the permutation of axes. Geometrically, this ensures that the intrinsic variation of the field—and the subsequent singular amplification—are distributed isotopically across the 3D domain.

We consider two scalar fields defined by composition with trigonometric functions:

$$u_{\tan}(x, y, z) = \tan(g(x, y, z)), \quad u_{\text{rec}}(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{\tan(g(x, y, z))}.$$

By the chain rule, their gradients can be expressed in a common factored form:

$$\nabla u_{\tan} = \sec^2(g) \nabla g, \quad \nabla u_{\text{rec}} = -\csc^2(g) \nabla g.$$

Thus, in both cases, the gradient separates into two components:

(a) a geometric variation term ∇g , and

(b) a trigonometric amplification term, given by $\sec^2(g)$ or $\csc^2(g)$, respectively.

The explicit gradient of g is given by

$$\nabla g(x, y, z) = (\tan(z) + y \sec^2(x), z \sec^2(y) + \tan(x), \tan(y) + x \sec^2(z)),$$

so that the geometric term $|\nabla g|$ varies smoothly across the domain and remains finite away from the poles of the tangent function.

Two mechanisms contribute to geometric features:

(i) Singular amplification (near poles).

For u_{\tan} , the factor $\sec^2(g)$ diverges when $\cos(g) = 0$, i.e.,

$$g = \frac{\pi}{2} + k\pi.$$

For u_{rec} , the factor $\csc^2(g)$ diverges when $\sin(g) = 0$, i.e.,

$$g = k\pi.$$

(ii) Geometric variation (bulk behavior).

The term $|\nabla g|$ acts as a bulk quantity, taking moderate values across the domain and encoding the intrinsic geometric variation of the field.

As a result, the magnitude of the gradient,

$$|\nabla u| = (\text{amplification}) \times |\nabla g|,$$

is governed by the interaction between a geometric component arising from the intrinsic variation of g and an amplification component induced by the outer trigonometric function.

3. Surface generation workflow

Iso-surfaces were extracted from the scalar field using the *Dodo* plugin for Rhino8/Grasshopper, followed by mesh refinement using the *Weaverbird* plugin (Fig. 2). The scalar field $u(x, y, z)$ was evaluated on a regular voxel grid over a bounded cubic domain

$$D = [-a, a]^3,$$

where the domain scale a was controlled by the Grasshopper parameter Factor. In the present implementation, this parameter was applied in units of π , so that the effective domain extent was scaled proportionally to $\pi \cdot \text{Factor}$.

The grid resolution was controlled by the parameter Number, which determines the voxel sampling resolution D_N and thus the fidelity of the extracted iso-surface. From the sampled values $u(x_i, y_j, z_k)$, an iso-surface was extracted at level

$$u(x, y, z) = c,$$

resolution fixed to ensure consistent feature clarity.

The selection of these models serves a dual purpose: to demonstrate the parametric design space and to explore the distinct sculptural qualities emerging from the proposed construction. The resulting forms range from folded shell-like enclosures (S1) and continuous rotational loops (S2) to lattice-like porous structures (S3), radially extending formations (S4), clustered branching geometries (S5), and ribbon-like circulatory forms (S6).

Crucially, these models were chosen for the visual legibility of their underlying mathematical structure; the interplay between singular amplification, branching, and surface continuity is directly perceptible. Beyond their mathematical significance, the physical realizations—evaluated through surface texture and spatial presence—highlight the sculptural character of the field.

These six models exemplify a diversity that emerges not from external, heuristic design but from the intrinsic structural logic of the scalar field itself. This spontaneity mirrors natural morphologies, such as coral and fungal mycelium, where complex, organic forms arise from simple underlying rules. Consequently, the selection of these models represents a process of discovery: navigating a parameter space where the scalar field reveals latent sculptural possibilities, much as a sculptor explores the expressive potential of a material.

Figure 3. Iso-surface models generated from u_{tan} . Models S1–S3 are shown: (a, b) S1, (c, d) S2, and (e, f) S3. For each model, two views are presented: a lateral view (left) and a frontal view (right). The parameter settings are as follows: S1 ($a = 5.22714$, $D_N = 5$, $c = 0.79407$), S2 ($a = 2.543562$, $D_N = 5$, $c = 1.41929$), and S3 ($a = 2.9839$, $D_N = 5$, $c = 0.93925$). The parameter a is implemented as a scalar multiple of π . The sampling resolution was fixed at

$D_N = 5$ for all models. Variations in domain scale and iso-value result in distinct geometric configurations while preserving the underlying structural characteristics of the field. Color mapping is applied to the radial distance from the origin using the *Turbo* colormap to enhance depth perception.

Figure 4. Iso-surface models generated from u_{rec} . Models S4–S6 are shown: (a, b) S4, (c, d) S5, and (e, f) S6. For each model, two views are presented: a lateral view (left) and a frontal view (right). The parameter settings are as follows: S4 ($a = 1.717509$, $D_N = 5$, $c = 0.92271$), S5 ($a = 7.22$, $D_N = 5$, $c = 0.71297$), and S6 ($a = 0.904932$, $D_N = 5$, $c = 1.19879$). The parameter a is implemented as a scalar multiple of π . The sampling resolution was fixed at $D_N = 5$ for all models. As in Fig. 3, variations in domain scale and iso-value

produce diverse geometric configurations while maintaining the same underlying structural framework. Color mapping is applied to the radial distance from the origin using the *Turbo* colormap.

4.2 Gradient decomposition

The structure of the iso-surfaces can be understood more precisely by examining the decomposition of the gradient derived in the Mathematical Formulation. As shown previously, the gradient of the scalar field can be expressed as a product of two components: a geometric variation term $|\nabla g|$ and a trigonometric amplification term ($\sec^2(g)$ or $\csc^2(g)$, depending on the formulation).

To investigate their respective roles, we visualize the value distributions of these components directly on the extracted iso-surfaces (Fig. 5). In this representation, the geometric variation term is shown in blue, while the amplification term is mapped in red.

A key observation is that the high-value regions derived from each component are distributed over the entire surface and appear spatially intertwined. The geometric variation term forms a continuous field that extends across the surface, while the amplification term is also present throughout, with its distribution concentrated near regions of strong structural variation, such as ridges and edges.

Figure 5. Visualization of gradient value distributions on the iso-surfaces for six representative models. (a–c) correspond to models S1–S3 generated from u_{\tan} , where the amplification term $\sec^2(g)$ is shown in red and the geometric variation term $|\nabla g|$ in blue. (d–f) correspond to models S4–S6 generated from u_{rec} , where the amplification term $\csc^2(g)$ is shown in red and $|\nabla g|$ in blue. The distributions are mapped onto the surface to illustrate the spatial interplay between the amplification and geometric components of the gradient.

4.3 Distance Dependence of Amplification

To further examine the relationship between singular amplification and geometric variation, we analyze the dependence of the gradient magnitude $|\nabla u|$ on the distance to the singular set. The distance is defined as

$$d = |(g \bmod \pi) - \frac{\pi}{2}|$$

for the tangent-based model, and as

$$d = \min(g \bmod \pi, \pi - (g \bmod \pi))$$

for the cotangent-based model.

Scatter plots of $\log_{10}(|\nabla u|)$ as a function of d are shown for representative cases of the tangent-based and cotangent-based constructions (Fig. 6). Prior to computing the logarithm, values of $|\nabla u|$ exceeding 10^{12} were capped. This threshold was chosen because, near the singular set, the amplification factors $\sec^2(g)$ and $\csc^2(g)$ diverge theoretically without bound; in floating-point arithmetic, however, extremely large values introduce numerical instability that obscures the underlying trend rather than illuminating it. The threshold of 10^{12} corresponds to values several orders of magnitude larger than those observed in the bulk of the surface, and its application affects only a negligible fraction of the sampled points. The qualitative structure of the scatter plots — in particular, the monotonic increase of $|\nabla u|$ as $d \rightarrow 0$ and the presence of large gradient values away from the singular set — is preserved independently of the precise choice of threshold, confirming that the observed two-mechanism behavior is not an artifact of the capping procedure.

In both models, a clear tendency is observed: as $d \rightarrow 0$, the values of $|\nabla u|$ increase significantly. This behavior reflects the singular amplification induced by the outer trigonometric function, where $\sec^2(g)$ or $\csc^2(g)$ diverges near their respective singular

sets.

However, the scatter plots also reveal that large values of $|\nabla u|$ are not restricted to regions close to the singular set. Even at moderate or large values of d , substantial gradient magnitudes are observed. This indicates that proximity to the singular set is not a sufficient condition for large $|\nabla u|$.

These observations suggest the presence of two distinct contributing mechanisms. Near the singular set, the amplification term dominates and produces sharp increases in $|\nabla u|$. Away from the singular set, large gradient values arise from the intrinsic structure of the field g , where $|\nabla g|$ itself becomes large.

Taken together with the relation

$$\nabla u = A(g) \nabla g,$$

these results indicate that the formation of sharp geometric features is governed by the interplay between singular amplification and the intrinsic gradient structure, rather than by singularity alone.

Importantly, this qualitative behavior is consistently observed across all examined models, including both tangent-based and cotangent-based formulations, suggesting that the distance-dependent amplification structure is a general characteristic of this class of constructions.

Figure 6. Distance dependence of gradient amplification.

(a) u_{\tan} model (S1, $n = 48,017$) with $A(g) = \sec^2(g)$. (b) u_{rec} model (S4, $n = 47,813$) with $A(g) = \csc^2(g)$. Scatter plots of $\log_{10}(|\nabla u|)$ as a function of distance d , where $d = |(g \bmod \pi) - \frac{\pi}{2}|$ for u_{\tan} and $d = \min(g \bmod \pi, \pi - (g \bmod \pi))$ for u_{rec} . Similar trends were observed across all other models. To exclude extreme outliers prior to logarithmic transformation, values of $|\nabla u|$ exceeding 10^{12} were capped.

5. Fabrication and Physical Realization

All iso-surface models presented in this study were fabricated using layered 3D printing to confirm their physical realizability (Fig. 7 (a)–(f)). To further explore their potential as sculptural objects, two selected models (S4 and S5) were additionally fabricated using full-color 3D printing (Fig.8 a, b). The color information was assigned based on the distance from the origin, following the default gradient of Grasshopper. In addition, one model (S2) was fabricated using metal 3D printing (Fig.8 c). These fabrication results demonstrate that the

proposed scalar field formulations not only generate mathematically interesting surfaces but also produce physically realizable forms suitable for applications in mathematical art and design.

Figure 7. Iso-surface models S1–S6 fabricated using layered 3D printing, demonstrating their physical realizability: (a) S1, (b) S2, (c) S3, (d) S4, (e) S5, and (f) S6.

Figure 8. Selected models fabricated as sculptural objects: (a) S4 and (b) S5 shown as full-color 3D prints using the default Grasshopper gradient; (c) S2 shown as a metal 3D print.

6. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, we introduced tangent-based scalar fields and their reciprocal forms as a framework for iso-surface generation, extending conventional sine–cosine constructions such as those used in triply periodic minimal surfaces [1]. The inner function g was designed to couple the three spatial coordinates cyclically, distributing singular amplification across the domain while preserving rotational symmetry under cyclic permutation of the axes. This design contrasts with prior approaches to sharp-feature implicit modeling, in which localized geometric transitions are introduced through explicit augmentation of an underlying smooth field [8]; in the present study, sharp features arise intrinsically from the mathematical structure of the scalar field itself.

The results show that the generated structures depend on domain scale and iso-value, with a rich variety of forms observed across parameter settings (Fig. 3, 4). Gradient analysis reveals

that sharp features arise from the combined effect of a smoothly varying geometric term and a singular amplification term (Fig. 5). This interpretation is consistent with the level set framework, in which the gradient of a scalar field governs the geometric structure of the surface [5]. While large gradient values increase near singular sets, they also occur away from them, indicating that both the inner function and the outer trigonometric amplification independently contribute to geometric complexity (Fig. 6). The numerical capping of extreme gradient values applied prior to logarithmic transformation does not affect these qualitative conclusions, as the two-mechanism behavior is consistently observed across all examined models regardless of the threshold choice.

The six models presented were selected not only to illustrate parametric variation but also to explore distinct sculptural qualities — including enclosure, branching, and directional flow — that emerge from the proposed scalar-field constructions. All generated models were successfully fabricated by 3D printing, confirming their physical realizability; selected models were additionally produced in full-color and metal to explore their potential as sculptural objects (Fig. 7, 8). The fabricated forms were evaluated not only as mathematical illustrations but as physical objects whose surface texture, translucency, and spatial presence contribute to their sculptural character. The formal diversity observed across the six models — ranging from enclosing shell-like structures to branching and ribbon-like forms — is reminiscent of natural morphologies such as coral, fungal mycelium, and skeletal structures that emerge from simple

underlying rules, suggesting that the singular amplification of the tangent-based field operates as an intrinsic generative principle analogous to those found in nature.

These results demonstrate that tangent-based scalar fields with singular amplification provide a flexible and expressive framework for iso-surface-based design, extending beyond conventional smooth and periodic formulations [1, 5, 6]. Beyond the specific constructions presented here, this framework suggests a broader class of scalar fields in which outer functions exhibiting rapid growth or singular behavior can modulate underlying geometric variations. In particular, other functions with divergent or near-divergent behavior may produce related but distinct structural characteristics when composed with spatially varying inner functions. These directions may further expand the applicability of implicit surface methods in both mathematical visualization and sculptural design.

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8. References

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